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ANALYSIS OF THE MECHANISM OF ETHICAL GOVERNANCE OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY ON SCIENTIFIC AND TECHNOLOGICAL INNOVATION

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Abstract. The uncertainty of the rapid development of science and technology has led to ethical risks that have attracted attention from all parties. As an important guarantee for the effective development of scientific and technological innovation activities, the ethical governance is of key significance to promote research and development innovation and ensuring that science and technology serve the greater good. An important issue in both governmental governance and academic discussions is how ethical governance of science and technology can enhance scientific and technological innovation. Based on the panel data at the prefecture-level cities from 2019 to 2023, the fixed effects model and the mediating effect model are used to test the impact of ethical governance of science and technology on scientific and technological innovation. The results show that ethical governance has a significant positive driving effect on scientific and technological innovation, and at the same time, ethical governance of science and technology promotes the improvement of innovation ability through the construction of legal environment. Accordingly, refining the ethical governance system of science and technology, adapting governance strategies flexibly, and optimizing the legal environment are essential to fostering sustainable scientific and technological innovation within an ethical framework.

Keywords: *ethical governance of science and technology, scientific and technological innovation, legal environment, empirical analysis.*

Rezumat. Incertitudinea dezvoltării rapide a științei și tehnologiei a condus la riscuri etice care au atras atenția tuturor părților implicate. Guvernanța etică a științei și tehnologiei este de o importanță cheie pentru promovarea inovației și pentru asigurarea faptului, că știința și tehnologia servesc binelui comun. O problemă importantă atât în discuțiile despre guvernanță guvernamentală, cât și în cele academice este modul în care guvernanța etică a științei și tehnologiei poate îmbunătăți inovația. Pe baza datelor panel din orașe la nivel de prefectură din 2019 până în 2023, modelul efectelor fixe și modelul efectului de mediere sunt utilizate pentru a testa impactul guvernanței etice asupra inovației științifice și tehnologice. Rezultatele arată, că guvernanța etică a științei și tehnologiei are un efect pozitiv semnificativ

și, în același timp, promovează îmbunătățirea capacității de inovare științifică și tehnologică prin construirea unui mediu juridic. În consecință, ajustarea sistemului de guvernare etică a științei și tehnologiei, adaptarea flexibilă a strategiilor de guvernare și optimizare a mediului juridic sunt esențiale pentru promovarea inovației științifice și tehnologice durabile într-un cadru etic.

Cuvinte cheie: *guvernare etică a științei și tehnologiei; inovație științifică și tehnologică; mediu juridic; analiză empirică.*

1. Introduction

Scientific and technological innovation is an important internal driving force for economic development and social progress [1]. Moreover, it serves as a key indicator for assessing social competitiveness [2]. Scientific and technological innovation receives significant global attention [3], not only as a driver of economic and social development but also as a means to address pressing challenges, including climate change [4], ecological degradation [5], and public health crises [6]. In the context of globalization, countries have enhanced their international competitiveness by promoting scientific and technological innovation. The government plays a pivotal role in this process [7]. Scientific and technological innovation is a complex and systematic work, which involves the interaction and integration of multiple innovation elements. This process is closely dependent on government support, guidance, and regulation, while simultaneously necessitating enhanced governance capabilities.

With the rapid development of science and technology, some fields have entered the innovation pioneer zone. The more advanced and complex the technology, the greater the potential ethical risks [8]. The limited precedents and governance experience of governments in addressing ethical risks in science and technology have hindered effective regulation, exacerbating issues such as trust [9], legal [10], medical [11], and social risks [12]. Strengthening the ethical governance of science and technology has become a critical component in enhancing the scientific and technological innovation system, with a well-developed legal framework playing a key role [13]. The government has strengthened the ethical governance of science and technology by establishing a robust legal framework. This includes standardizing key processes such as R&D, application, promotion, and technological transformation. These measures effectively mitigate ethical disputes, foster a favorable environment for innovation, and accelerate research and development progress. Thus, studying the impact of ethical governance on scientific and technological innovation is crucial for refining governance frameworks and fostering sustainable technological advancement.

Through the review of the existing literature, the research on ethical governance of science and technology and scientific and technological innovation mainly focuses on the following aspects. The first aspect focuses on analyzing various ethical risks associated with emerging technologies [14,15]. Additionally, countermeasures are proposed based on the principle of 'science and technology for good' [16]. The second aspect emphasizes the primacy of ethics in scientific and technological innovation [17]. It explores the fundamental connotation, practical foundations, and implementation mechanisms of ethical principles [18], while also advocating for responsible innovation [19]. Third, both ethical governance in science and technology and scientific and technological innovation require stronger legal frameworks [20,21], necessitating the establishment and refinement of a robust legal system for science and technology. In summary, most existing studies adopt qualitative research or

theoretical deduction, focusing on ethical challenges in scientific and technological innovation. However, quantitative evidence remains scarce on the relationship between ethical governance of science and technology and scientific and technological innovation. Particularly, further research is needed to explore how ethical governance policies influence the process and outcomes of scientific and technological innovation.

Building upon the identified research gaps, this paper constructs a theoretical framework and quantifies the abstract concept of 'ethics'. Quantitative methods are employed to examine the impact of ethical governance on scientific and technological innovation, revealing its underlying mechanisms and processes, and clarifying the dynamics and complexity of ethical governance implementation, thereby addressing the limitation of existing research that primarily relies on theoretical exploration. Furthermore, this study provides quantitative evidence to support government decision-makers and assists policymakers in balancing ethical considerations with technological advancements. Moreover, this research promotes adherence to ethical norms among scientific research institutions while fostering technological progress, offering theoretical and practical guidance for strengthening national competitiveness.

2. Theoretical analysis and research hypotheses

2.1 Ethical Governance of Science and Technology and Scientific and Technological Innovation

The ethical governance of science and technology establishes reasonable norms and frameworks for innovation, ensuring that scientific and technological activities comply with ethical standards and achieve a balance between innovation and ethics. First, such governance involves sociology, law, ethics, and other disciplines. Interdisciplinary collaboration introduces new perspectives and multidimensional insights for technology developers [22]. This expands developers' perspectives, stimulates new ideas, encourages broader considerations in technology development, and further enhances the depth and breadth of innovation output. Second, ethical governance prompts governments to introduce policies that regulate technology development [23]. These systems prevent technological innovation from descending into unregulated and ethically problematic situations, ensuring that R&D personnel operate in a stable and well-regulated environment to facilitate continuous technological progress. Meanwhile, ethical governance mitigates moral and legal risks in technological innovation, thereby accelerating innovation. Technological innovation is often accompanied by high risks and uncertainties, particularly when the technology is not yet mature [24]. Such uncertainties may lead to ethical controversies, hinder R&D, and even provoke legal and social opposition, ultimately impeding technological progress. However, ethical governance guidelines clarify rules for innovators, reduce external opposition and internal disagreements, and enable them to focus on technological breakthroughs, thereby facilitating the emergence of ethically compliant technologies. As the capital market pays increasing emphasis on ethical norms [25], the long-term social value of technological innovation has become a key determinant of investment decisions. As a result, innovative projects with a sound ethical foundation are more likely to gain investors' trust and support, thereby securing sufficient R&D resources and enhancing innovation efficiency. A high level of ethical governance ensures that scientific and technological achievements benefit society and fosters public recognition and support for technological innovation. Therefore, ethical governance of science and technology is not merely a regulatory framework for technological

innovation but also a crucial driver of innovation and development. Based on the above analysis, the following hypotheses are proposed:

Hypothesis 1: Ethical governance of science and technology has a positive impact on scientific and technological innovation

2.2 The mediating effect of ethical governance of science and technology on the impact of scientific and technological innovation

The ethical governance of science and technology aims to curb misconduct and unlawful exploitation in science and technology while fostering technological innovation. The key to enhancing competence in ethical governance of science and technology lies in a well-established legal environment [26]. The authority of law serves to regulate scientific and technological innovation and ensure its alignment with societal interests and sustainability goals. The sound legal environment is essential for conducting innovative activities and enhancing innovation efficiency [27]. The legal establishes ethical and legal standards for scientific and technological innovation, ensuring that technology enterprises and researchers adhere to fundamental ethical and legal boundaries. Furthermore, legislation and regulation provide mechanisms to address social risks and ethical dilemmas associated with technological advancements, mitigating potential negative societal impacts.

Additionally, a fair legal environment promotes healthy market competition and fosters greater innovation dynamics. The legal is the institutional guarantee for ethical governance of science and technology [28], also clarifies the direction of development for scientific and technological innovation [29], and achieves a balance between ethics and legal, innovation and regulation. This shows that the ethical governance of science and technology realizes the effective restraint and optimization of scientific and technological innovation behavior through the legal.

The legal environment establishes stable rules and norms for scientific and technological innovation, enforces mandatory legal constraints [30], protects intellectual property rights, and stimulates technological R&D and innovation [31]. At the same time, it avoids ethical risks, ensures that innovations do not infringe on the rights of others, and follows the rules of lawful use and distribution [32].

A fair legal environment fosters a competitive and orderly market [33]. The healthy market requires market intermediary organizations to act as supervisors, increasing market scrutiny on scientific research, enhancing information transparency, and fostering healthy competition. Such competition encourages scientific research institutions to enhance their technical capabilities and refine product development strategies, ultimately facilitating the emergence of new technologies and products in the market.

Legal frameworks and market intermediary organizations jointly establish an ecosystem that ensures ethical compliance, safeguards innovation, upholds market order, and fosters scientific and technological advancement. Based on the above analysis, the following hypothesis is proposed:

Hypothesis 2: Ethical governance of science and technology has a positive impact on scientific and technological innovation through the legal environment.

3. Empirical design

3.1 Data Sources and Processing

The data in this paper are from the China National Intellectual Property Administration, the National Bureau of Statistics and the China Market Index Database, and all the

observations of the sample variables are collated and calculated by the author. The original data is processed as follows:

1. In order to ensure the accuracy and reliability of the data, the outliers and missing values are eliminated.

2. The average annual growth rate of the data from previous years is used to predict the data of China's marketization index by province from 2020 to 2023.

3. Prefecture-level cities belong to different provincial-level administrative units, and the work arrangement of the government at provincial-level directly affects the corresponding prefecture-level cities.

Therefore, the provincial-level and its corresponding prefecture-level administrative units were matched, and then data analysis and empirical research were carried out.

3.2 Variable declaration

3.2.1 Core explanatory variable

Ethical governance of government in science and technology (Gstg). This study uses text analysis to measure the level of ethical governance of science and technology. First, the "Guidelines on Strengthening the Governance over Ethics in Science and Technology" was divided into words and the words with a frequency of less than 2 were eliminated. 250 keywords were initially obtained. Then expert opinions were sought, and 28 keywords such as ethics of science and technology, artificial intelligence, public safety, and code of conduct were finally retained after manual review. Second, the frequency of keywords occurrence in the 31 provincial-level government work reports from 2019 to 2023 was extracted. Third, the frequency of keywords in the government work report should be logarithmically processed to measure the level of ethical governance of government in science and technology.

3.2.2 Explained variable

Scientific and technological innovation capability (Inno). This study selects the number of patent applications at the prefecture-level cities as an indicator of scientific and technological innovation capability. The number of patent applications directly reflects country or region ability to innovate in science and technology [34]. Moreover, this indicator is easy to quantify and allows for convenient data acquisition, making it a widely used measure in academic research. The study by Bendig et al. [35] demonstrates that the number of inventions is partly representative of scientific and technological innovation capability. Therefore, this study also uses the number of inventions applied for the same year at the prefecture-level cities (Inven) as an alternative measure of technological innovation capability to conduct robustness tests. Patent application data can accurately measure the innovation capability and competitiveness of core technological fields, while the number of inventions applied for the same year reflects the overall scale and activity of scientific and technological innovation. Both indicators provide a comprehensive evaluation of the level of scientific and technological innovation.

3.2.3 Mediating variable

Legal environment (law). Drawing on the research methods of scholars Liu and Jiang [36], the development of market intermediary organizations and the legal system environment are used as the measurement index of the legal environment.

3.2.4 Control variables

The control variables include the level of economic development (GDP), the state of human resource (human), and the condition of infrastructure (road). Table 1 shows the composition, classification and connotation of specific indicators.

Table 1

Variable Selection and Measurement Methods				
Variables type	Variables name	Variable symbol	Measuring method	Data source
Explained variable	Scientific and technological innovation capabilities	Inno	The number of patent applications at the prefecture-level cities	China National Intellectual Property Administration
Core explanatory variable	The level of ethical governance of science and technology	Gstg	The frequency of the occurrence of keywords related to "ethical governance of science and technology" in the provincial-level government work report was extracted, and the natural logarithm was taken	Work report of the provincial-level government
Mediating variable	Legal environment	law	An index of the development of market intermediary organizations and the legal system environment	China Market Index Database
Control variables	The level of economic development	GDP	GDP per capita	National Bureau of Statistics
	The state of human resource	human	Resident population at the end of the year	National Bureau of Statistics
	The condition of infrastructure	road	Highway mileage	National Bureau of Statistics

3.3 Model construction

3.3.1 Benchmark regression model

The fixed effects model is constructed in the empirical evidence to investigate the impact of ethical governance of science and technology on scientific and technological innovation. In this model, two types of non-observed effects are generally controlled, namely individual fixed effects and point-in-time fixed effects. The former reflects the influence of background factors on the explained variables that change with individuals but not at any point in time.

The latter represents the effect of background factors on the explained variables that varies at any point in time but does not vary with the individual. Therefore, we construct the panel data econometric model with a double-fixed effect of individual point-in-time effect as the benchmark regression model, as shown in Eq. (1).

$$Innovation_{it} = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 Gstg_{it} + \alpha X_{it} + \mu_i + \mu_t + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (1)$$

In Eq. (1), $Innovation_{it}$ represents the scientific and technological innovation ability of region i in period t . $Gstg_{it}$ represents the level of ethical governance of science and technology of region i in period t . X_{it} represents a series of control variables. μ_i represents individual fixed effects. μ_t represents a point-in-time fixed effect. ε_{it} is a random perturbation term that obeys an independent and identical distribution.

3.3.2 Mediating effect regression model

To further explore the specific influencing mechanism between ethical governance of science and technology and scientific and technological innovation, that is, to test whether there is a mediating effect in the legal environment, the following mediating effect model is constructed based on the benchmark regression model:

$$law_{it} = \delta_0 + \delta_1 Gstg_{it} + \delta X_{it} + \mu_i + \mu_t + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (2)$$

$$Innovation_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 Gstg_{it} + \beta_2 law_{it} + \beta X_{it} + \mu_i + \mu_t + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (3)$$

Where the law_{it} represents the mediating variable. α_1 reflects the total effect of ethical governance of science and technology on scientific and technological innovation, β_1 reflects the direct effect of ethical governance of science and technology on scientific and technological innovation, $\delta_1\beta_2$ reflects the magnitude of the mediating effect, and $\delta_1\beta_2/\alpha_1$ represents the proportion of the mediating effect in the total effect, reflecting the importance of mediating variables in the ethical governance of science and technology to promote scientific and technological innovation. If α_1, β_1 and β_2 are all significant, but β_1 is smaller than α_1 , it indicates that there is a partial mediating effect. If both α_1 and β_2 are significant, but β_1 is not, it indicates a complete mediating effect.

4. Empirical results and analysis

4.1 Descriptive statistics of variables

The descriptive statistics of each variable are shown in Table 2. Among them, the maximum value of the core explanatory variable is 6.000, the minimum value is 0.000, and the standard deviation is 1.377, indicating that there are significant differences in the level of ethical governance of science and technology among different provinces. The maximum value of the explained variable is 320.813, the minimum value is 0.001, and the standard deviation is 23.450, which indicated that there are great differences in the performance of scientific and technological innovation in different regions. The descriptive statistical results of the remaining variables are shown in the table, and the data are generally standardized without obvious outliers.

Table 2

Descriptive Statistics						
Variable	Numbers	Mean	StdDev	Min	Median	Max
Gstg	1387	1.620	1.377	0.000	1.000	6.000

Continuation Table 2

Inno	1387	9.640	23.450	0.001	2.869	320.813
GDP	1387	6.910	2.173	3.471	6.461	15.049
human	1387	5972.150	3238.825	590.000	5047.000	12706.000
road	1387	16.690	10.751	0.000	16.900	40.540
law	1387	12.840	3.359	0.871	12.552	23.955

Note: Inno - scientific and technological innovation capabilities; Gstg - the level of ethical governance of science and technology; law - legal environment; GDP - the level of economic development; human - the state of human resource; road - the condition of infrastructure; StdDev - standard deviation. Source: Authors' computation.

4.2 Benchmark regression results and analysis

The benchmark regression results are shown in Table 3. Column (1) only added the core explanatory variable, the regression coefficient is 0.203, passed the significance test at the 10% level. Column (2) further adds control variables, and the regression coefficient of the core explanatory variable is 0.275, which is significant at the 5% level. The regression results show that ethical governance of science and technology has a significant positive impact on scientific and technological innovation, and validates the proposed theoretical hypothesis¹. The ethical governance of science and technology creates a secure and transparent environment, encouraging enterprises and research institutions to prioritize the legitimacy and ethical implications of technology, thereby fostering the sustainable development of scientific and technological innovation.

Furthermore, ethical governance of science and technology enables scientific and technological innovation to anticipate and mitigate potential ethical risks, thereby reducing the likelihood of failure for new technologies and enhancing their market competitiveness. Additionally, it fosters the disclosure and collaboration of scientific and technological achievements, leading to an increase in patent applications for innovative outcomes while ensuring that these results are legally protected and socially recognized.

The results of the control variables were basically in line with expectations. The regression coefficient of human capital condition is significantly negative at the 10% level, and the regression coefficient of infrastructure condition is significantly positive at the 1% level, indicating that these two are important influencing factors.

The negative impact of human capital on scientific and technological innovation may stem from talent shortages, mismatches, brain drain, and insufficient incentive mechanisms, which constrain the contribution of scientific and technological talents and reduce innovation efficiency[37]. The positive impact of infrastructure conditions underscores their supportive role in scientific and technological activities. Infrastructure, such as roads, provides a more conducive physical and social environment for scientific and technological innovation[38]. It further facilitates resource flow, promotes information exchange, and fosters industrial clusters, thereby reducing logistics costs, enhancing R&D and production efficiency, and accelerating cross-regional scientific and technological cooperation.

The insignificance of other control variables may be attributed to measurement biases. However, these variables interact with each other, collectively fostering sustainable economic development and overall societal progress.

Table 3

Benchmark Regression Results		
Variable	(1) Inno	(2) Inno
Gstg	0.203* (1.70)	0.275** (2.28)
GDP		-0.703 (-1.63)
human		-0.001* (-1.65)
road		0.142*** (3.63)
_cons	9.311*** (40.64)	15.201*** (4.22)
City_FE	YES	YES
Year_FE	YES	YES
N	1387	1387
R ²	0.970	0.970
Adj. R ²	0.96	0.96

Note: ***, **, and * indicate significance at the 1%, 5%, and 10% levels, respectively. Clustering robust standard errors are reported in parentheses. Inno - Scientific and technological innovation capabilities; Gstg - The level of ethical governance of science and technology; GDP - The level of economic development; human - The state of human resource; road - The condition of infrastructure; _cons - Constant; City FE - City fixed effects; Year FE - Year fixed effects; N - Number of observations; R² - R-squared; Adj. R² - Adjusted R-squared. Source: Authors' computation.

4.3 Endogeneity tests

The fixed effects model of the benchmark regression reveals that ethical governance of science and technology significantly promotes scientific and technological innovation. However, endogeneity issues, including proxy variable measurement errors and unobserved omitted variables, may introduce biases in model estimation. Therefore, an instrumental variable approach was employed to mitigate the estimation bias caused by endogeneity in measuring the impact of ethical governance on scientific and technological innovation.

The marketization presents ethical dilemmas of science and technology that challenge the governance mechanisms of human society [39]. The higher degree of marketization corresponds to more developed factor market. Developing the factor market promotes the ethical governance of science and technology and mitigates the negative effects of disruptive scientific and technological innovations. The factor market primarily influences resource allocation[40], which in turn affects enterprises' and research institutions' access to funding and talent. However, whether breakthroughs in scientific and technological innovation can be achieved depends more on the innovation environment, key actors, and inputs [41], and these factors are not strictly constrained by factor markets. Therefore, the factor market satisfies the correlation and exogeneity requirements for instrumental variables. Following Zhang et al. [42], this study adopts the degree of factor market development (DFM) as an instrumental variable. The results of endogeneity test are shown in Table 4. From the test results, can be seen that after adding the instrumental variable of the degree of factor market development, the improvement of the level of ethical governance of science and technology still significantly improves the ability of scientific and technological innovation. In addition,

the Kleibergen-Paap rk LM statistic was 74.444, $P = 0.000$; the Kleibergen-Paap rk Wald F statistic was 61.821, which was much greater than the Stock-Yogo test cut-off of 16.38 at the 10% level; the endogeneity test statistic was 4.783, $P = 0.0287$. The above results show that the tool variables are valid.

Table 4

Endogeneity Test Results		
Variable	(1) Gstg	(2) Inno
DFM	0.448*** (0.0569)	
Gstg		1.257** (0.536)
GDP	-0.366*** (0.108)	-0.536 (0.454)
human	0.000142 (8.76e-05)	-0.000833** (0.000389)
road	-0.0561*** (0.00940)	0.199*** (0.00940)
City_FE	YES	YES
Year_FE	YES	YES
N	1387	1387
Kleibergen-Paap rk LM		74.444***
Kleibergen-Paap rk Wald F		61.821
Endogeneity test		4.783**

Note: ***, **, and * indicate significance at the 1%, 5%, and 10% levels, respectively. Clustering robust standard errors are reported in parentheses. DFM - The degree of factor market development; Inno - Scientific and technological innovation capabilities; Gstg - The level of ethical governance of science and technology; GDP - The level of economic development; human - The state of human resource; road - The condition of infrastructure; City FE - City fixed effects; Year FE - Year fixed effects; N - Number of observations; Kleibergen-Paap rk LM - Kleibergen-Paap rank lagrange multiplier statistic; Kleibergen-Paap rk Wald F - Kleibergen-Paap rank wald f statistic. Source: Authors' computation.

Then, the lagged period of the core explanatory variable (1Gstg) was used as the instrumental variable to perform the endogeneity test again, and the regression results are shown in Table 5. After the core explanatory variable lags for one period, the coefficient of 1Gstg is significantly positive at the level of 5%, which is not significantly different from the benchmark regression results, which indicates that the causal relationship will not significantly interfere with the estimation results in the same period, further indicates that the research conclusion is robust.

Table 5

Endogeneity Test Results:One Lag Period		
Variable	(1) Inno	(2) Inno
lGstg	0.605** (2.53)	0.576** (2.40)
GDP		-4.377***

Continuation Table 5

		(-4.96)
human		0.002 (1.31)
road		-0.145** (-2.44)
_cons	10.099*** (23.53)	30.313*** (2.94)
City_FE	YES	YES
Year_FE	YES	YES
N	1085	1085
R ²	0.957	0.959
Adj. R ²	0.94	0.94

Note: ***, **, and * indicate significance at the 1%, 5%, and 10% levels, respectively. Clustering robust standard errors are reported in parentheses. Inno - Scientific and technological innovation capabilities; 1Gstg - The level of ethical governance of science and technology is lagging behind; GDP - The level of economic development; human - The state of human resource; road - The condition of infrastructure; _cons - Constant; City FE - City fixed effects; Year FE - Year fixed effects; N - Number of observations; R² - R-squared; Adj. R² - Adjusted R-squared. Source: Authors' computation.

4.4 Robustness tests

First, replace the explained variable. The number of inventions applied for the same year (Inven) replaces the number of patent applications and conducts robustness test. The number of inventions applied for the same year reflects the introduction of innovative technologies and new solutions within the region, indicating that such innovations often lead to new production methods, process improvements, or practical solutions. It also serves as a comprehensive measure of the region's R&D capacity, technological progress, and innovation policies. As shown in Table 6, the regression coefficient in column (1) is 0.060 without control variables, which is statistically significant at the 5% level, while the coefficient in column (2) increases to 0.074 after adding control variables, achieving statistical significance at the 1% level. These findings indicate that the ethical governance of science and technology plays a significant role in promoting scientific and technological innovation, confirming the robustness and reliability of the benchmark regression results.

Second, increase control variable. To further address potential endogeneity arising from omitted variables, additional control variable by using financial expenditure on science and technology (finance) was incorporated following the research framework proposed by Han et al. [43]. With this expanded set of control variable, the benchmark regression model was re-estimated. The regression results, presented from columns (3) to (4) of Table 6, indicate that the coefficient for financial expenditure on science and technology is 2.294, which is statistically significant at the 1% level. This finding suggests that increased financial expenditure on science and technology strengthens the impact of ethical governance on scientific and technological innovation. These findings further support the robustness and reliability of the benchmark regression results.

Third, the observation time is replaced. the variable observation period of 2019 was deleted and replaced with from 2020 to 2023. In 2019, China established the National Science and Technology Ethics Committee and convened the Fourth Plenary Session of the 19th Communist Party of China Central Committee in October, which clearly emphasized the need to enhance the scientific and technological innovation system. To ensure the robustness and

validity of the results, the variable observation period in 2019 is deleted in this section and the robustness test regression is carried out due to special macroeconomic fluctuations and policy adjustments or changes in the industry structure. As shown in Table 6, the regression coefficient in column (5) remains significantly positive at the 10% level without control variables, while in column (6), after incorporating control variables, the coefficient is significantly positive at the 5% level. These findings further confirm the robustness and reliability of the benchmark regression conclusions.

Table 6

Robustness Test Results						
Variable	(1) Inven	(2) Inven	(3) Inno	(4) Inno	(5) Inno	(6) Inno
Gstg	0.060** (2.16)	0.074*** (2.64)	0.203* (1.70)	0.323*** (2.66)	0.287* (1.87)	0.383** (2.45)
finance				2.294*** (2.61)		
_cons	2.749*** (51.60)	2.773*** (3.30)	9.311*** (40.64)	7.054 (1.48)	9.112*** (31.20)	21.190*** (4.23)
CVs	NO	YES	NO	YES	NO	YES
City_FE	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
Year_FE	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
N	1387	1387	1387	1387	1100	1100
R ²	0.985	0.985	0.970	0.970	0.964	0.965
Adj. R ²	0.98	0.98	0.96	0.96	0.95	0.95

Note: ***, **, and * indicate significance at the 1%, 5%, and 10% levels, respectively. Clustering robust standard errors are reported in parentheses. Inven - Scientific and technological innovation capabilities; Inno - Scientific and technological innovation capabilities; Gstg - The level of ethical governance of science and technology; finance - Financial expenditure on science and technology; _cons - Constant; CVs - Control variables; City FE - City fixed effects; Year FE - Year fixed effects; N - Number of observations; R² - R-squared; Adj. R² - Adjusted R-squared. Source: Authors' computation.

4.5 Mediating effect results and analysis

To explore the specific influence mechanism, the analysis is conducted from the perspective of the legal environment. The regression results are shown in Table 7, with column (1) presenting the benchmark regression. Column (2) takes the legal environment as the explained variable, showing that the regression coefficient in ethics governance of science and technology on legal environment is 0.052, which is significantly positive at the 10% level, indicating that an improvement in ethics governance of science and technology enhances the legal environment. In column (3), the legal environment was included in the benchmark regression as control variable, and the regression coefficient in ethics governance of science and technology is 0.264, which is significantly positive at the 5% level, while the regression coefficient of the legal environment is 0.214, significantly positive at the 10% level, suggesting a partial mediating effect of the legal environment. Therefore, the results confirm that the ethics governance of science and technology enhances scientific and technological innovation capacity through the legal environment, supporting Hypothesis 2.

The mediating effect of the legal environment is primarily reflected in strengthening the construction of the law system [44], improving the level of rule of law [45], and carrying out

governance in accordance with laws and regulations [46]. These factors collectively contribute to the high-quality development of scientific and technological innovation while fostering a secure and well-regulated environment. Improving the legal in the ethical governance of science and technology is essential for ensuring scientific and technological activities adhere to ethical values and behavioral norms, it required compliance with laws and regulations throughout the entire innovation process, including scientific research and technology development [47], thereby fostering responsible innovation. By strengthening the legal framework, which not only helps control risks and minimize losses but also upholds fundamental ethical principles, ensuring a balanced interaction between innovation, development, and risk prevention [48].

Table 7

Mediating Effect Test Results			
Variable	(1) Inno	(2) law	(3) Inno
Gstg	0.275** (2.28)	0.052* (1.84)	0.264** (2.19)
law			0.214* (1.67)
_cons	15.201*** (4.22)	14.967*** (17.57)	11.995*** (2.94)
CVs	YES	YES	YES
City_FE	YES	YES	YES
Year_FE	YES	YES	YES
N	1387	1387	1387
R ²	0.970	0.918	0.970
Adj. R ²	0.96	0.90	0.96

Note: ***, **, and * indicate significance at the 1%, 5%, and 10% levels, respectively. Clustering robust standard errors are reported in parentheses. Inno - Scientific and technological innovation capabilities; Gstg - The level of ethical governance of science and technology; law - Legal environment; _cons - Constant; CVs - Control variables; City FE - City fixed effects; Year FE - Year fixed effects; N - Number of observations; R² - R-squared; Adj. R² - Adjusted R-squared. Source: Authors' computation.

To further verify the rationality of the mediating effect of the legal environment, the Sobel test is used to estimate the effect of ethical governance of science and technology on scientific and technological innovation through the legal environment, and the results are shown in Table 8. The indirect, direct, and total effects all show significant positive values, confirming the existence of this mediating effect. Moreover, the indirect effect is 0.042, the direct effect is 0.346, and the total effect is 0.389, with the mediating effect accounting for 10.89% of the total effect. This further demonstrates that ethical governance of science and technology has a partial mediating effect on scientific and technological innovation, while the direct effect remains dominant.

Table 8

Sobel Tests Results				
	Route	Coefficient	Sobel Z	Proportio
Indirect Effect	Gstg→law→In	0.042*	1.659	10.89%
Direct Effect	Gstg→Inno	0.346**	2.000	89.11%
Total Effect		0.389**	2.264	100%

Note: ***, **, and * indicate significance at the 1%, 5%, and 10% levels, respectively. Inno - Scientific and technological innovation capabilities; Gstg - The level of ethical governance of science and technology; law - Legal environment; Sobel Z - Sobel Z-test statistic. Source: Authors' computation.

5. Conclusions and recommendations

5.1 Research conclusion

This paper compiles panel data at the China's prefecture-level cities from 2019 to 2023 and employs fixed effects model along with mediating effect model to analyze the impact of ethical governance of science and technology on scientific and technological innovation. The empirical results show that:

1. Ethical governance of science and technology has a significant positive impact on scientific and technological innovation, meaning that improving ethical governance can significantly enhance scientific and technological innovation capabilities.

2. The legal environment plays a mediating role in this relationship, indicating that ethical governance of science and technology promotes scientific and technological innovation by optimizing the legal environment.

5.2 Management inspiration

China is at a critical juncture in its innovation-driven development strategy. With the rapid advancement of the new scientific and technological revolution, scientific and technological innovation has not only driven economic growth but also led to profound transformations in healthcare, energy, and academia, generating substantial social benefits. However, overlooking the ethical risks of technological innovation may lead to potentially irreversible and catastrophic consequences, especially in artificial intelligence, biotechnology, and data privacy. Ethical governance of science and technology has become a key component of global governance. Maximizing the role of ethical governance in scientific and technological innovation is a pressing theoretical question that requires urgent attention. Drawing on the findings of this study, we present the following implications:

Firstly, the governance mechanism of science and technology should be further improved. Some typical ethical incidents in science and technology that have sparked public debate have exposed deficiencies in the ethical supervision mechanism of science and technology and the oversimplification of the research evaluation system. Majorities of the public believes that government regulation plays a central role in strengthening ethical governance in science and technology and ensuring technological security. Therefore, it is necessary to reinforce the government's leadership in ethical governance of science and technology, address various ethical challenges in science and technology, and ensure that scientific and technological innovation develops in a responsible and beneficial manner. And then, grassroots departments are key implementers of policies, making local governments key supervisors in regulating scientific and technological activities. This requires local governments to establish dedicated regulatory agencies to carry out ethical compliance reviews and safety assessments of scientific and technological innovation projects on a regular basis, establishing a standardized and systematic workflow to ensure a rigorous and impartial review process. Finally, the government should establish a public feedback mechanism and set up public opinion collection channels, disclose the decision-making process and ethical review results of scientific and technological innovation projects to encourage public participation in decision-making, and ensure effective feedback implementation.

Secondly, accelerating the legislative process of science and technology ethics is essential to providing a strong legal guarantee for governance. The legalization of science and technology ethics can effectively prevent and mitigate ethical risks in the field of scientific and technological innovation. It is necessary to elevate the ethical review and evaluation of scientific and technological activities to the institutional level and impose appropriate penalties for violations of ethical norms in science and technology. The government should formulate a top-level system, follow legal and regulatory requirements to intervene within appropriate boundaries, and embed ethical governance into R&D and application. Given the professional, complex, and evolving nature of science and technology ethics, the enactment of a basic law on science and technology ethics, along with specialized laws targeting key areas, is crucial to establishing a comprehensive legal framework. Facilitate the establishment of an institutional system for ethical governance of science and technology at all levels, address specific domains and ethical concerns, and propose targeted measures for different types of ethical issues. Furthermore, based on the principles of minimum ethical standards, protection of private rights, and safeguarding of public interests, ethical risk management in scientific and technological innovation should be ensured through mandatory legal measures. At the same time, policies should be adjusted as needed to ensure a responsive and adaptable ethical governance model.

6. Research insufficient

This paper conducts an in-depth analysis of the relationship between the ethical governance of science and technology, scientific and technological innovation, and the legal environment, offering valuable insights for governments to formulate management policies and enhance regional innovation levels. However, there are certain limitations that future research should address. Firstly, the sample is based on panel data at the China's prefecture-level cities from 2019 to 2023. The controversial case of 'gene-edited babies' by Jiankui He's team in 2018 represents a major violation of scientific and ethical principles, highlighting the disorder and risks associated with technological advancements in the absence of ethical constraints. As a result, drawing widespread academic attention, the number of published papers on science and technology ethics has increased significantly since 2019. Consequently, data collection on this study began in 2019. Future studies could further refine the dataset and expand the scope of collection to enhance the persuasiveness of the findings.

The scope of mediating variables in this study is relatively limited and does not fully capture all potential influencing factors. Theoretical analysis suggests that the legal environment plays a mediating role; however, future research could further explore the critical roles of social trust and public acceptance of technology. From the perspective of social norms, social trust influences policy implementation, serving as a fundamental moral basis for an orderly society and shaping the ideas and decisions of policymakers and implementers. From the perspective of people's livelihood services, the public's acceptance of technology affects the success of scientific and technological innovation. Skepticism toward a technology may lead to policy restrictions and reduced market demand, thereby hindering the innovation process, whereas positive public attitudes can drive investment and support rapid technological advancements. Therefore, future research should strive to overcome these limitations by incorporating a broader range of mediating factors for more in-depth and systematic analysis.

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